

FROM LAB TO FIELD: EVALUATING DEEP LEARNING ROBUSTNESS FOR PLANT DISEASE RECOGNITION

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Abstract:

Deep learning models for plant disease recognition often achieve high accuracy on curated laboratory-style datasets, yet their performance can drop sharply when applied to real-world images captured under uncontrolled conditions (illumination changes, cluttered backgrounds, varying viewpoints, and mixed symptoms). This work presents a reproducible lab-to-field evaluation that quantifies this generalization gap and assesses which practical choices improve robustness when transferring from curated to in-the-wild data.

We study cross-domain transfer from PlantVillage (curated source) to PlantDoc (in-the-wild target). To ensure methodological rigor, we adopt a conservative label alignment restricted to eight unambiguous disease classes shared across both datasets (potato early/late blight and multiple tomato diseases). We further curate the target set by separating atypical samples for review, producing a “clean” PlantDoc subset with 1,793 images overall and 594 aligned test images for the eight-class protocol. On the source side, we compare two balanced training subsets with 200 samples per class (1,600 total): (i) random sampling and (ii) diversity-based sampling using embedding-space clustering to better capture intra-class variability.

Experimental results indicate that data selection is a dominant factor for cross-domain robustness. Using a ResNet18 baseline, random sampling achieves 21.4% accuracy and 17.3% macro-F1 on the aligned PlantDoc test set, whereas diversity-based sampling improves performance to 26.8% accuracy and 22.1% macro-F1. In contrast, switching to larger backbones (EfficientNet-B0 and ViT-B/16) under the same training budget does not consistently improve transfer, and naive symptom splitting by uniform cropping can reduce macro-F1, highlighting the importance of symptom-aware curation. All experiments are tracked in a structured SQLite-based pipeline to ensure transparency and reproducibility.

These findings emphasize that improving robustness in real-world plant disease recognition may depend more on data-centric strategies (curation and diversity-aware sampling) than on increasing model capacity alone, motivating future work toward locally collected field datasets and deployment-oriented evaluation.

Keywords : deep learning; domain shift; robustness; plant disease recognition; reproducible evaluation